

Monolithic Multi-Channel SiGe Quantum Key Distribution Transmitter Chip

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Abstract—Quantum key distribution (QKD) allows the secure transmission of encryption keys in the dawning age of quantum computers. However, despite photonic integration efforts, the size and complexity of current QKD systems remains a roadblock for practical deployment in cost-sensitive applications. Here we show a monolithic integrated QKD transmitter that exclusively builds on silicon photonics. We introduce a germanium-on-silicon light emitter acting as source for a co-integrated quantum state encoder, to generate a secure key over a 45.9 km field-installed fiber link. On top of this, we demonstrate the broadband operation of our QKD transmitter by generating keys over 32 wavelength channels, making it an integrated colorless QKD transmitter with full C-band coverage. Employing monolithic silicon technology paves the way towards fully integrated optoelectronic QKD transmitters, enabling a drastic reduction of size and cost while benefiting from the maturity and mass production capabilities of complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor (CMOS) technology. Moreover, omitting the need for rare and costly III-V semiconductor materials to generate light can drastically reduce the overburdening assembly and packaging requirements inherent to optoelectronics, potentially enabling QKD to finally enter new application domains closer to the consumer market.

Index Terms—Light sources, quantum communication, quantum cryptography, quantum key distribution, silicon photonics.

I. INTRODUCTION

EVERYDAY billions of credit card payments, authentication processes or confidential messages are transmitted over optical networks. Privacy and secure transmission are an uncontested necessity for this type of exchanged data. With

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the rise of the quantum computer [1], [2], which is able to efficiently execute prime factorization [3], the security of the widely employed public key infrastructure based on asymmetric cryptography is greatly threatened. Quantum key distribution (QKD) can counter this burgeoning threat, offering information-theoretic security since it relies on the laws of quantum physics to generate symmetric keys between two parties for subsequent data encryption.

Today, QKD is in the process of moving from labs and early-stage field trials to first real-world deployments at national and continental scales [4]. However, present-day QKD setups remain bulky and expensive, with a single transmitter and receiver occupying at least one standard 19-inch server rack slot. At this point, a disruptive simplification of QKD is required for it to move out of a niche market and become a much more pervasive solution – one that reaches till the very end of communication networks.

Since the key exchange facilitated through prepare-and-measure QKD schemes only requires the unidirectional transmission of a quantum-optic signal in parallel to a bidirectional classical channel that serves the key distillation process, an extra degree of freedom is gained when practically integrating QKD into networks: The hub-and-spoke layout of optical networks closer to the edge enables their operators to centralize bulky and costly equipment at suitable locations (such as central offices or public kiosks). In the case of the provenly secure BB84 protocol, being the most widely implemented discrete-variable QKD (DV-QKD) variant, the involved single-photon detectors are considerably contributing to the overall system complexity, especially due to their cooling requirements. The QKD receivers are therefore the prime choice for a centralized element and can be pooled and shared among multiple users that are equipped with vastly simplified and therefore inexpensive QKD transmitters. By being able to provide a vast amount of cheap, reliable and small transmitter devices, QKD can enrich novel application domains, furnishing access networks and smoothly blending into handheld devices.

Research has responded to this practical implementation challenge through a continuous and systematic miniaturization of QKD devices during recent years [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], taking advantage of steadily maturing photonic

Fig. 1. State of the art in QKD and electronic microprocessor integration, including the herein presented monolithic silicon QKD transmitter.

integration platforms (Fig. 1). A few peculiarities can be observed towards this direction: First, hetero-integration platforms such as polymer [5], [6], [7] are primarily attractive to implement specific quantum-optic sub-systems requiring optical nonlinearities, such as entangled photon sources. However, these platforms are not destined for monolithic integration. Second, InP platforms suit the fabrication of monolithic solutions for prepare-and-measure systems [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Nonetheless, III-V materials feature higher wafer costs due to the excessive involvement of critical raw materials such as In, Ga or As, and additionally require hermetic packaging. They further hinder the seamless photonic-electronic co-integration since microelectronic circuits are predominantly realized on silicon-based CMOS technology, such as introduced in Fig. 1 for the particular case of mobile-device microprocessors. This alignment with the silicon microchip ecosystem is beneficial as it removes exposed interfaces between quantum-optics and electronics, which render current systems more prone to tampering.

The third group of photonic integrated QKD sub-systems is based on silicon platforms [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], which benefit from the generational advances of CMOS technology [35]. Although quantum state-preparation has been demonstrated on rather small form-factors, the absence of a native gain medium on silicon necessitates these works to optically supply the QKD circuits with hetero-integrated III-V light sources [34]. This requires precise waveguide-to-waveguide alignment and results in prohibitive assembly and, again, hermetic packaging costs, which typically amount to a high share of 90% in the overall device cost [36].

This work presented herein extends our initial investigation [37] of a monolithic silicon QKD transmitter realized through light emission of a SiGe light source native to silicon chip fabrication. We combine this emitter with electro-optic phase-modulators and polarization management on a single silicon integration platform to demonstrate polarization-encoded BB84 DV-QKD at a secure-key rate of 655 b/s and a QBER of 5.05% over a 45.9 km field-deployed fiber link. In addition, we show that our transmitter can generate secure keys over 32 ITU-T wavelength channels without the need for additional light sources. The exclusively silicon-centric layout paves the way towards fully integrated optoelectronic QKD transmitter

solutions that can be provided with a disruptive downscaling of today's form-factors and cost.

This manuscript is organized as follows. Section II introduces the concept of the SiGe light emitter and the all-silicon transmitter, while Section III highlights the experimental framework that has been used to evaluate the monolithic silicon PIC. Section IV discusses the QKD performance in the lab while Section V then reports the performance for a deployed fiber link. Finally, Section VI concludes the work.

II. SiGe LIGHT EMITTER AND SILICON TRANSMITTER

The photonic integrated circuit (PIC), shown in Fig 2, was fabricated on IMEC's iSiPP50G silicon-on-insulator platform [38]. The employed light emitter is a forward-biased SiGe PIN junction that is laterally implemented along a 90 μm long waveguide section, which interfaces to the interconnecting waveguides through tapered sections at its front and rear facets. The Ge region on top of the junction waveguide is 300 nm thick. Single-polarization 1-dimensional and polarization-combining 2-dimensional grating couplers (GC) are employed for out-of-plane coupling at the optical ports of the QKD transmitter PIC. The 1D-GC directly interfaces with the rear facet of the light source and is solely used for the purpose of source characterization, while the 2D-GC is part of the quantum state preparation circuit that is fed by the front facet of the light source. The PIC includes two phase modulation sections, of which the first (PM1) is dedicated to the flexible distribution of light among the waveguide branches of PM2-X and PM2-Y, whose optical phases can be independently set. One of the branched modes is subsequently converted from transverse electric (TE) to transverse magnetic (TM) through the 2D-GC that launches the constructed polarization state into an ITU-T G.652B-compatible single-mode fiber (SMF). Furthermore, the symmetry of the overall circuit design, as well as the precise fiber alignment, ensures that the coupling is optimal for both waveguides launched by the 2D-GC. 2×2 multi-mode interference couplers (MMI) are employed as compact interconnect elements within the QKD transmitter. With these components the state encoding can be performed as follows (Figs. 2 and 5): Since each waveguide branch at PM2 corresponds to one of the two principal polarization states **H** and **V** due to the reference provided by the 2D-GC at the PIC output, the preceding section PM1 can be used to set the optical power ratio between **H** and **V** via the RF signals Z and \bar{Z} (Fig. 2). In this way, either **H**, **V** or **D** can be generated, the latter state corresponding to an equal distribution of power in **H** and **V**. In this balanced case, PM2 can introduce an optical phase shift to generate any state along the S_2/S_3 -plane of the Stokes space via the RF signals X and Y . Thus, the circular states **R** and **L** can be encoded (Fig. 5), as can be any arbitrary polarization state on the Poincaré sphere.

The SiGe source has a LED-like emission that reaches a light output of -64.5 dBm, corresponding to 354.8 pW, at a forward current of $I_F = 30$ mA (Fig. 3(a)) and an emission of -65.4 dBm at $I_F = 25$ mA. The forward current I_F dependent characteristics can be modelled as

$$V_F^* = V_t \ln \left(\frac{I_F}{I_S} + 1 \right) + R_S I_F, L^* = \kappa I_F^2 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Fabricated PIC hosting the all-silicon QKD transmitter, including a schematic drawing of the SiGe light emitter as well as the employed building blocks such as grating couplers (GC), multi-mode interference couplers (MMI), thermo-optic (TOPS) and electro-optic phase shifters / modulators (PM). Furthermore, the RF signal feeds and routing lines are indicated by Z, \bar{Z} , X and Y.

Fig. 3. (a) VLI characteristics of the SiGe source including the design model and (b) temperature dependence. (c) Spectral emission at the 1D- and 2D-GC. (d) Transmitter output upon direct source modulation for carving and decoy-state transmission.

Fig. 4. (a) VLI characteristics of the SiGe source for five different samples from wafer A and (b) wafer B. (c) Spectral emission of the same samples from wafer A and (d) wafer B.

174 where the parameters for forward voltage V_F and light output L
 175 of the fabricated device are $V_t = 0.2\text{V}$, $I_S = 100\ \mu\text{A}$, $R_S = 43\ \Omega$
 176 and $\kappa = 0.65\ \text{nW/A}$ according to the limited efficiency of light
 177 generation in silicon. The measured light output L of the source
 178 shows saturation towards a higher drive current, as indicated
 179 by the difference from the unsaturated model L^* . Furthermore,
 180 as we noticed that forward currents in excess of 30 mA can
 181 lead to device breakdown, we consider this the limit for stable
 182 long-term operation of the source. In addition, we evaluated the
 183 source emission for different temperatures from 25°C up to 80°C
 184 (Fig. 3(b)). As can be seen the output power shows only a minor
 185 decrease of 1 dB at 80°C compared to room temperature.

The spectral distribution of the source emission was in-
 186 vestigated with a single-photon spectrometer with a detection
 187 efficiency of $-17\ \text{dB}$. Its broadband emission spectrum Λ is
 188 centered in the C+L band region (Fig. 3(c)), rendering it suitable
 189 for low-loss fiber transmission. For a 1D-GC directly extract-
 190 ing the light output L_{1D} of the source, the peak emission is
 191 5.2 pW/nm at 1564 nm, with a FWHM bandwidth of
 192 46 nm.
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Due to the different designs of the 1D-GC and 2D-GC, these
 194 elements feature different peak emission wavelengths and band-
 195 widths. As a result, when acquiring the emission L_{2D} after pass-
 196 ing through the entire state-preparation circuit, the emission of
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Fig. 5. Experimental setup for evaluation of the QKD PIC via a VOA, SMF lab fiber spools and a field-installed fiber. The inset and Poincaré sphere show the validation of the state generation performed with an external III-V source and classical detectors.

the 2D-GC peaks at 1546.5 nm. As for the 1D-GC employed for source characterization, the 2D-GC emission is well aligned to the wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) grid specified for optical fiber communication, which eases the integration of the QKD transmitter in classical networks as we will demonstrate in Section IV. Similar spectral characteristics can be achieved when compared to our previously investigated vertical die-level and laterally waveguide-coupled emitters [39], [40], yet at a nearly one order-of-magnitude (9.5 dB) improvement in output power. This is crucial to accommodate the additional optical loss of ~ 19.5 dB due to the relatively long electro-optic phase modulators of the co-integrated polarization-encoder. This, together with the spectral filtering loss due to channel definition, will result in an average photon number of $\mu < 0.1$ photons/symbol, corresponding to a power of -88.9 dBm when operating the QKD transmitter at a symbol rate of $R_{Sym} = 100$ MHz. As we will prove shortly, this does not prevent us from generating a secure key.

The impedance of the source permits direct modulation of the forward current I_F for the purpose of pulse carving, to improve the security of the key exchange, as well as to adopt the transmission of decoy states [41]. For direct source modulation we used an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight M8195A) to modulate the bias current of the source that is adapted to a 50Ω impedance. Its optical output, filtered by a 200-GHz bandpass, was then acquired by a SPAD connected to a time tagging module (TTM, AIT TTM8000). The TTM was synchronized to the AWG in both, clock frequency and frame repetition rate, enabling us to record a histogram of the detected SPAD counts. Fig. 3(d) shows the source response to super-Gaussian pulse carving to 5 ns, equaling half of the symbol width, including random decoy pulses. The intensity of the decoy pulses was chosen in such a way that the received number of photons corresponds to 50% of the maximum output power to adhere to a one-decoy-state BB84 protocol [42].

We further investigated the emission of the SiGe source across different samples from two different wafers (Fig. 4(a)–(d)). As shown, the VLI characteristics of all samples are nearly identical, with an average emission of -65.1 dBm ($\sigma = 0.29$ dBm) at

$I_F = 25$ mA. Furthermore, also the spectral emission between the different samples shows a good uniformity, confirming a reliable design of the grating coupler. This is confirmed by the overlap of the distinct spectral peak at 1584 nm, which was introduced on purpose by a non-optimized coupling angle of 9° and is absent when the angle is optimized, as it was the case in Fig. 3(c).

III. QKD EVALUATION AND CHARACTERIZATION SETUP

Fig. 5 presents the experimental setup for the evaluation of the monolithic integrated QKD transmitter. The bare PIC was tested on an opto-electronic probe-station that provides an interface with optical fibers and electrical high-frequency and biasing probes. We used single-mode fibers at an optimized angle of 10° for out-of-plane coupling and the PIC was temperature controlled to $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ to improve the stability with respect to the bias points of its constituent elements. Due to the limited number of four available drive channels of our AWG, we resorted to continuous light emission of the SiGe source at a bias of 25 mA without pulse carving or decoy states for the QKD measurements. While freeing an AWG channel for source carving by using only a single EOPM per section is possible in principle, the necessary voltages in this case would have exceeded the modulator limits significantly, leading to permanent damage. However, the continuous emission does not limit the validity of our results since carving and decoy states do not influence the state generation but are rather employed for security reasons and to suppress symbol transitions. The four symbol states of a polarization encoded BB84 protocol [43], [44] are encoded by the waveform generator at a rate of $R_{Sym} = 100$.

To mitigate depolarization caused by the incoherent light emission of the source optical filtering is paramount as already investigated earlier [39]. We therefore employed an optical bandpass filter (BPF, β in Fig. 8(a)) with a flat-top transmission T_{BPF} that features a bandwidth of $\Delta\lambda = 200$ GHz centered at 1550.12 nm (ITU-T channel 34) and an insertion loss of 0.8 dB. In a realistic network deployment, this BPF would be replaced by a WDM multiplexer. Since the QKD signal of the quantum channel λ_Q is launched with an average photon number

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Fig. 6. (a) TOPS calibration via reverse light injection at different polarizations and (b) temperatures. (c) EOPM drive calibration via detection of forward light injection by the monitor PIN diodes.

of $\mu = 0.015$ photons/symbol at the output of this filter, no additional power leveling is required to comply with the BB84 QKD protocol. Due to this already weak emission, we did not consider narrower optical filters as a practical option. The QKD signal was then transmitted either through a variable optical attenuator (VOA) to probe the tolerable optical budget between QKD transmitter and receiver, standard SMF lab spools, or over a field-installed fiber link in Vienna.

At the QKD receiver the received signal was manually aligned to the axes of a fiber-based polarization analyzer (PA), whose optical outputs correspond to the six polarization states **H**, **V**, **D**, **A**, **R** and **L**. For reception of the QKD signal either a pair of in-house built free-running InGaAs single-photon avalanche photodiodes (SPAD) with a quantum efficiency of 8%, a dead-time of 10 μs and dark count rates of 308 and 251 s^{-1} , or NbTiN based superconducting nanowire single photon detectors (SNSPD, SingleQuantum EOS 210 CS), with a detection efficiency of 65%, a dead-time of 50 ns and dark count rates of 75 and 123 s^{-1} were employed, followed by a TTM that records the detection events with a resolution of 82.3 ps. Off-line analysis then involved frame synchronization, temporal filtering through digital reduction of the acceptance window to 5 ns equal to 50% of the symbol width, basis sifting, quantum bit error ratio (QBER) evaluation, raw-key (RKR) generation and secure-key (SKR) estimation.

We would like to mention that we expect carving to further improve our herein presented results, since it would reduce the share of correct detections/bits which are eliminated by the digital temporal filtering while increasing the detections

in the acceptance window, resulting in higher key rates. As already mentioned, the carving should not influence the state generation and thereby the intrinsic QBER of the transmitter. However, a slight reduction of the QBER can be expected through carving. This is because the total bit rate increases, while the errors induced through detector dark counts within the acceptance window remain constant.

Initial calibration and characterization of the QKD transmitter was performed in the classical power regime. Factory calibration of the first phase section PM1 can be achieved via the integrated thermo-optic phase shifters (TOPS, Fig. 2). Therefore, reverse light is injected through the 2D-GC and detected with the co-integrated monitor PIN diodes ($PIN_{1,2}$) as well as the SiGe source, which can be re-used as a detector yielding the photocurrent I_{SiGe} . To balance the optical power between the TE and TM branches and to set a phase reference, the bias point is fixed to a point of equal power in both branches (α , Fig. 6(a)). As Fig. 6(b) shows, this bias point is stable with rising temperature. We further calibrated the fast electro-optic phase modulators (EOPM) for RF modulation and determined $V_\pi = 4.6$ V via light injection through an alternative 1D-GC input port and detection with the monitor PIN diodes (Fig 6(c)).

To first characterize the state generation of the QKD transmitter a time-resolved Stokes vector analysis was then performed in the classical power regime. For this purpose, a laser operating at $\lambda_C = 1547.72$ nm is externally coupled to the PIC to source our polarization-encoder circuit via the alternative 1D-GC input. As the optical bandwidth of the employed components on the PIC significantly exceeds that of the grating couplers, characterization at a single wavelength close to the 2D-GC center wavelength of 1546.5 nm is sufficient. At the receiver side we then employed balanced detectors in the three output bases of the PA and recorded the corresponding Stokes vector $S = (S_1, S_2, S_3)$ through a fast real-time oscilloscope (Agilent DSO-X 91604). For evaluation a pseudo-random bit sequence was used as key seed for state preparation and the transmitted BB84 bases were switched randomly. As can be seen in the time-domain signals $S_1 \dots S_3$ that are presented as an inset in Fig. 5, there are two clear three-level signals received in the S_1 (corresponding to **H/V**) and S_3 (**R/L**) bases, while there is no signal in the S_2 basis (**D/A**). For each of the presented signals, the highest/lowest level corresponds to a bit '1' or '0' being transmitted in the respective basis, while due to balanced photodetection the intermediate level corresponds to a bit being sent in one of the other two bases. The correct state generation is confirmed by the Poincaré sphere inset in Fig. 5. Thus, the classical characterization confirms the correct functionality of our integrated quantum state-preparation circuit.

IV. MONOLITHIC QKD TRANSMITTER PERFORMANCE

We first investigated the QKD performance as a function of the optical link budget (OB) and different photon/symbol values μ through emulation of lightpath loss via a VOA (Fig. 7(a)), comparing the baseline performance of the externally sourced polarization-encoder (λ_C in Fig. 2) to the fully monolithic QKD

Fig. 7. (a) Evaluation of the supported OB / μ for the externally/internally sourced PIC. (b) QKD performance over link reach.

Fig. 8. (a) 2D-GC emission (grey), OTF (rainbow, γ) and BPF (black, β) filter transmission. (b) Wavelength-dependent QKD performance.

transmitter that is powered by its own SiGe light source (Λ in Fig. 5).

For the baseline performance, we achieve a QBER of $6.38\% \pm 0.27\%$ at a RKR of 51.2 kb/s for an OB of 0 dB (\bullet in Fig. 7(a)) and can accommodate up to 16.8 dB of link loss before surpassing the QBER limit of 11% for secure-key extraction [45]. This budget is equivalent to an end-of-life fiber loss of 61 km of SMF, considering the conservative end-of-life fiber loss of 0.277 dB/km of our lab fiber samples. We then switched to the fully monolithic silicon QKD transmitter. There is no performance penalty apart from the reduced launch power of $\mu = 0.015$ photons/symbol, which reduces the dynamic range in link budget. This proves that the incoherent silicon light emission, which achieves an OB of $\Gamma = 8.7$ dB, before reaching the QBER limit, can sufficiently supply the QKD transmitter. We further expect that an improvement of the SiGe source emission towards $\mu = 0.1$ photons/symbol at a 1 GHz rate,

which is readily supported by the employed EOPMs, will lead to state-of-the-art RKR in the Mb/s range [11], [30]. Furthermore, in this case expected high rates should further contribute to an enhanced secure-to-raw key ratio than currently accomplished, as evidenced by the currently reached QBER of $2.68\% \pm 0.18\%$ at a RKR of 86.1 kb/s, in the InGaAs SPAD saturation limit (ϵ , Fig. 7(a)).

We then investigated the impact of possible fiber-induced performance penalties for the fully monolithic QKD transmitter through concatenation of SMF spools (Fig. 7(b)). We can generate raw-keys at a QBER below the 11% threshold for a transmission distance of up to 31 km. In view of the back-to-back results presented before, the compatible reach of 31 km with its loss of $\Xi = 8.5$ dB for the fiber stack indicates that there is no significant penalty induced due to fiber transmission since $\Xi \approx \Gamma$.

To demonstrate how the broadband emission of the SiGe source can be harnessed to provide spectral flexibility for the QKD transmitter, we further investigated the channel-dependent QKD performance. For this, the thin-film filter based BPF at the output of the QKD transmitter (β in Fig. 8(a)) has been replaced with a 200-GHz wide tunable optical filter with an average insertion loss of 3.9 dB (γ). Fig. 8(b) shows the performance for transmission over 4.3 km of SMF and acquisition in one measurement basis (H/V), for QKD operation from 1520.25 to 1576.20 nm. While the maximum RKR of 4.4 kb/s/basis coincides with the spectral maximum of the light emission, we reach a QBER of $8.81\% \pm 0.33\%$ for channel 34, yielding the maximum SKR of 591 b/s/basis [46]. In general, the RKR follows the spectral emission L_{2D} of Fig. 3(c) and 8(a) while the QBER increases towards the S- and L-band emission borders, where the dark counts gain a larger share within the acquired detector counts. We can generate secure keys over a wide spectral window, ranging from the upper S-band to the lower L-band, covering a large number of 32 ITU-T WDM channels on a 200-GHz grid over the entire C-band. Under the assumption of a full BB84 QKD implementation with four detectors we achieve a SKR of >1 kb/s for eleven of these channels, each of them providing a sufficient number of keys to secure a classical channel capacity of 12 Tb/s of classical data traffic considering the AES-GCM limit for single-key use derived from [47], with a standard nonce length of 96 bit as required by RFC5116, a standard Ethernet message payload of 1500 bytes and an

Fig. 9. (a) Deployed fiber link in Vienna, (b) its characterization by means of OTDR and (c) polarization drift.

Fig. 10. Long-term QKD performance over field-installed fiber.

upper bound on the attack probability of 2^{-60} complying with TLS 1.3. In addition, 20 additional channels provide enough keys to secure classical data links with capacities of up to 2 Tb/s, which is sufficiently high considering low-cost commodity applications. These results demonstrate the broadband nature of the monolithic silicon QKD transmitter. Following the notion of WDM-based passive optical networks [48], this can enable the secure communication of 30 users connected to a centralized receiver station through standard WDM technology, by using the same colorless QKD transmitter PIC at every network user. Alternatively, this also enables a simplified choice of the QKD wavelength for network integration, without the need to change the laser source or emission characteristics – as it would be the case for traditional QKD transmitters.

V. QKD PERFORMANCE OVER FIELD-INSTALLED FIBER LINK

In a final step we used the SNSPD-enhanced QKD receiver to test our transmitter over a deployed fiber link in Vienna (Fig. 9(a)), which originates at AIT and loops back at the University of Vienna. The total link length and loss are 45.9 km and 16.5 dB, respectively (Fig. 9(b)). We noticed a strong background of ~ 7 kcts/s upon connection of the dark fiber link to our QKD receiver. This background is attributed to ambient light coupling to the SMF at any of the 28 cross-connect points due to exposure of connectors or partially transparent fiber jackets. However, adding a second 200-GHz BPF before our QKD receiver (Fig. 5) enabled us to suppress this background to a level below the dark count level of the SNSPDs. We were then able to achieve a RKR of 1.55 kb/s at a QBER of 5.1%,

which is well below the QBER threshold of 11%. This yields a SKR of 655 b/s and enables us to secure a classical channel capacity of 7.8 Tb/s according to the AES-GCM limit.

We further acquired the RKR and QBER over a full hour to evaluate the stability of our QKD transmitter (Fig. 10). We noticed a nearly constant RKR, confirming stable operation of the SiGe source on the monolithic QKD transmitter PIC. At the same time, the QBER slowly increases. This is attributed to the polarization drift along the field-deployed fiber, which is confirmed by additional classical measurements that indicates a polarization evolution of 7 mrad/min for the overall fiber link (Fig. 9(c)). Automated polarization control based on a per-basis QBER indicator would have to be employed at the QKD receiver to maintain a continuously low QBER, similar as indicated by the manual re-alignment at the end of the measurement period (δ , Fig. 10).

VI. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated a monolithic silicon QKD transmitter, based on a polarization-modulated SiGe light emitter, and have proven its capability to generate a secure key over a 45.9 km deployed fiber link. We have further shown that the broadband emission of the silicon-centric source is constant and reproducible among multiple samples and that a telecom-centric wavelength grid can be harnessed to facilitate a colorless QKD transmitter. This opens avenues towards its deployment in wavelength-multiplexed network architectures that allow for virtual point-to-point links between a centralized head-end (hosting a QKD receiver) and many low-cost, field-deployed tail-end units (furnished by QKD transmitters), as introduced in classical optical access and mobile fronthaul networks. The availability of a highly simplified QKD transmitter, as enabled through the monolithic silicon integration scheme, contributes squarely to this mission: First, the omission of rare and thus costly III-V semiconductors through an exclusively silicon-based approach that is streamlined with the highly efficient silicon-based microelectronic ecosystem permits the integration of QKD in cost-sensitive application fields, such as short-reach networks or hand-held devices. Second, the compatibility with CMOS technology allows for a seamless co-integration of all the photonic and electronic circuitry required for QKD operation, including CMOS-based QRNG functions [49]. This further advances the scale of integration towards tamper-proof chip-scale QKD solutions at the smallest possible form-factor.

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